

Research and Innovation

July 2024

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region's economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find the results of the second round of data collection during 2023 and the first months of 2024 and a comparison with the baseline data collected in the previous round.

In terms of Research and Innovation, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator "Summary Innovation Index" and on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Note
Data for Kosovo* not available

Source
European Innovation Scoreboard 2022. EU countries and neighbouring countries database
https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard_en#eis-interactive-tool
(accessed 21 February 2024).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

WB Steering Platform meetings		
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Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Supporting Western Balkans reforms for science & research alignment with EU acquis Participation in European programmes, initiatives and schemes

| | Technical assistance (TA) to Chapter 25 (Science and Research) reforms |
|-------------------------------|---|--|--|--|---|
| Albania | Low level of bilateral TA projects and Twinning projects
Low uptake of TAIEX missions |
| Bosnia and Herzegovina | Bilateral TA projects increased
Twinning projects and TAIEX missions remain a challenge |
| Kosovo* | Low level of bilateral TA projects and Twinning projects
Low uptake of TAIEX missions |
| Montenegro | Low level of bilateral TA projects and Twinning projects
Low uptake of TAIEX missions |
| North Macedonia | Low level of Twinning projects and bilateral TA projects
No new TAIEX missions taken up |
| Serbia | No new Twinning or bilateral TA projects reported
Low level of TAIEX missions uptake remains a challenge |

Legend: Information not available

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Highlights

Western Balkans partners successful in the 2023 EIT HEI Initiative

Further ERA integration by increased number of joint projects and mobilities with EU Member States

